

“Democracy Dies In Darkness” - An Explorative Study on the Exploitation of Women in India

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Abstract

India is a developing country where women are facing exploitation in every facet of their life to live their life peacefully. The declining sex ratio is a negative sign which projects exploitation of women in a crystal clear format. Women are being exploited physically, mentally, economically and socially. Crimes against women are in various forms or structures. It is inclusive of crimes against female genital mutilation, adultery, prostitution, trafficking, rapes, dishonest misappropriation, domestic violence, dowry problem are all the injurious hazards to the society. Rape is one of India's most universal crimes against women. Official sources show that rape cases in India has been doubled. India has been named as the most dangerous country for women in the world-in the recent survey conducted by Thomson Reuter's foundations in the year 2018. For rape there is no fixed time in India, women should always be alert. No democracy is a democracy when half of its population lives in fear. It is high time to take steps to solve the problem of exploitation.

Introduction

Exploitation means, “The practice of taking selfish or unfair advantage of a person or situation, usually for personal gain”. Encarta Dictionary (2009)

Exploitation usually occurs when two unequal forces come in contact. India is a developing country where women are facing exploitation in every facet of their life to live their life peacefully. The declining sex ratio is a negative sign which projects exploitation of women in a crystal clear format. Women are being exploited physically, mentally, economically and socially. Exploitation of women are taking place everywhere, but only very few cases are exposed by the media. There are umpteen number of cases of women exploitation remain unexposed. The challenges of women are rape, kidnapping, trafficking, dowry, molestation, workplace harassment, sexual harassment, and many more. The researcher has attempted to find out the Indian perspectives women exploitation in this dynamic world.

Position of Women

Women in pre-Vedic period enjoyed a comparatively high status during the early Vedic period. At later stage, the position of men started growing and women were not able to retain her position.

The position of woman was day by day worsened during medieval period. Many philanthropists were given their strong opposition to exploitation of women during east India Company period. Later in Uslampatti area of TamilNadu, “Feared of Dowry parents killed their girl babies”. Same kind of situation prevailed in other state too. The Sex ratio had dipped drastically. In other parts of a country like Punjab, bearing a son is a prestige issue and female foeticide increased. The status of women in the current scenario has been improved but not virtually. They spend most of their time for the well being of their family. The constitution of India states that women have equal status to men. But women are ill-treated inside and outside the home physically as well as mentally.

Literature Review

- Anitha, Sundari (2019) Understanding economic abuse through an intersectional lens: Financial abuse, control and exploitation of South Asian women’s productive and reproductive labours. Violence against Women. ISSN 1077-8012. stated that financial abuse focuses on men’s control over money, goods, and assets and over women’s education/work, thereby implicitly constructing economic activity as paid work. This particular article discusses under-recognition of men’s (and in the context of particular communities, their family’s) abuse of and control over women’s unpaid (domestic) labour within a broader conceptualization of economic abuse. This article gives an intersectional perspective to explore how gender, migration status, ethnicity and class can help understand women’s experiences as a continuum of economic abuse.
- Taylor and Francis online journal on Critical review of International school and Political philosophy published an article, “Art and politics of imagination: remembering mass violence against women” This paper addresses the role of creative memory in processes of redressing political violence and historical injustices. The argument is that inventive memory work can foster collective reminiscences of the painful past in ways in which to overcome both individual and national representations. This article describes the political potentialities of new artistic models of demoralization, namely participatory and collaborative artistic practices. The usual media, can commemorate victims collaboratively, simultaneously catalyzing transnational cohesion.
- Manikamma Nagindrappa, *Radhika M.K. in their article, Women Exploitation in Indian modern society, International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 3, Issue 2, February 2013 1 ISSN 2250-3153 1 identified that We should urge political will must translate into concrete action and stronger implementation of already existing laws and regulations. Though we have safeguards in our country, the women in India continue to suffer, due to lack of awareness of their rights, illiteracy and oppressive practices and customs. This article tries to understand the stages and an array of under privileged section via the exploitation of women in present society. To suggest Create healthy atmosphere for women and girls all over the place by supporting efforts to stop violence against them through the education and make muscular laws to penalize victim immediately.

Objectives of the Study

- To explore the reason for exploitation of women
- To find out the solution to control exploitation of women

Phases of Women Exploitation

At the WOMB

Women are victimized at every facet of their life. Exploitation starts when she is at the womb of her mother. Even today, the moment it is diagnosed as girl child abortion takes place in many

parts of our country. It may be due to various reasons like considering girls as burden or the misconception of the family about the breadwinner concept. There are people who still believe women are not as productive as men. Abortion after 18 weeks of pregnancy is a threat to the life of a mother and child. Their health is being ignored by the family.

As a Girl Child

She is being deprived of good nutritional foods and quality education. Due care and attention has not been provided by few parents. Most of the time she is being used as a care taker of her brother and unpaid household worker. Child trafficking is highly lucrative nowadays as most of them are ignorant about the violence against women.

As a Teenager

Adolescence is the most crucial part of any women's life. Highest number of trafficking, gang rapes, ragging, prostitution, early marriage and all these forms of exploitation happens at this stage. Psychological factors and the influence of social media play a major role here. Teens are being trapped by beauty, wealth, fame, and name. Adolescent child thinks that she is mentally, physically grown up and often ends up by taking deplorable decision.

As a Wife

The millennium project report of 2005 states that, "gender equality remains an unfulfilled goal". This is rightly applicable at this phase of women. As a wife she is being exploited by her husband, his friends, and her in-law's family, Exploitation happens in the form of physical, sexual, and mental state.

As a Workmate

Exploitation of women is little higher at this stage too. There is disparity in the work place. Starting from salary, work environment and work timings there is a difference. Women are being molested by higher officials at the office space.

As a Mother

She devotes her entire life for the welfare of the family at free of cost. As a mother she bring sup her kids as a responsible citizen. Ironically, she doesn't have any right in decision making of the family issues. At later stage of her life, she is been left alone.

As a Grandmother

She loses her beauty, health and productive nature. This absence of productivity often projects her as a burden to their family. She is helpless. At old age, with all health issues she is helpless. Most of the time she ends up as house servants or in the community halls. Indian women are facing the real trauma of exploitation. They are always leading an oppressed life.

Structure of Women Exploitation In India

Crimes against women are in various forms or structures. It is inclusive of crimes against female genital mutilation, adultery, prostitution, trafficking, rapes, dishonest misappropriation, domestic violence, dowry problem are all the injurious hazards to the society. Official sources show that rape cases in India has been doubled. Rape is the highest escalating crime in India compared to murder, theft and kidnapping. The report of National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), says for every 60 minutes, two women are raped in India. The biggest range of such crimes was reported from neighbors. One-quarter of the victims were minors, 27.9 percent of culprits were well-known to sufferers and 28.38 percent were associates and 8.35 from relations. These figures are underestimations as many incidents go unreported due to fear of stigma and non awareness of rights. Furthermore the innumerable cases of eve teasing, indecent gazes, pinching, brushes and comments that infringe upon the rights of women, especially in overcrowded spaces and public transport buses and trains. This necessitates for a radical transformation in attitudes and mindsets towards such

incidents. Poor investigations, harsh cross examination of victims, senseless adjournment of cases and faulty assessment of evidence and furnishing of evidence by victims in presence of culprits are areas that need reforms. Mostly this type of crimes is done by Neighbours, friends, relatives, employed/co-workers and known persons. This kind crime committed by the unknown persons are very meager, viz 3.68%. Women aren't safe even with their family, neighbours, relatives and known persons in present day world. As per 2016 statistics, in 94 % of rape cases, the criminals are Victim's father, brother, uncle, grand father or very close neighbours.

As per the 2016 statistics, under Section 376 and under Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act (POSCO) there are a total of 38,947 rape cases were registered in the year. Majority of girls and women keep calm but most also bury the pain and strain, pretend it has not happened. Perhaps pretending may help make it go away. It may help to overlook the pain and the terror. It may be post-trauma behaviour is culturally apt way of coping. Going dead on the inside. Feeling confused. Acting normal, using audacity, especially when work colleagues and bosses are close by. According to News 18 survey, 27 per cent of women have experienced physical violence ever since the age of 15 in India. This occurrence of corporeal violence among women is widespread in rural areas than among women in urban areas. Marital violence cases, where women reported bodily abuse in rural and urban areas, were at 29 per cent and 23 percent, respectively. 31% of married women have been victimized with physical, sexual, or emotional violence by their spouses. Every third women, since the age of 15, has faced domestic violence of various forms in the country, reported the National Family Health Survey (NHFS-4) released by the Union health ministry. Thus, incubating a new question about the cultural underpinnings to domestic violence. The crime record study reported that among married women who have experienced physical violence since the age of 15, 83 per cent reported their present husbands as perpetrators of the violence. On the other hand, for women who are not married, the experience of physical violence stems from the most common perpetrators, which include mothers or step-mothers (56%), fathers (33%), sisters or brothers (27%), and teachers (15%). However, the most distressing part of the spousal-violence is that approximately every third married women, who has experienced spousal violence, reported experiencing physical injuries, including eight per cent who have had eye injuries, sprains, dislocations, or burns and six per cent who have had deep wounds, broken bones, broken teeth, or any other serious injury. So far, only 14 per cent of women who experienced this violence sought help to stop it.

But the defenselessness of stopping the violence being inflicted on them isn't the only distressing factor. Women in backward countries, surprisingly, are supportive of domestic violence.

Data from the survey shows women in India between the ages of 40 to 49 were most supportive of domestic violence, with 54.8% in agreement. The percentage mitigating abuse is marginally lesser among younger women. 47.7% of girls flanked by the age of 15 and 19 agreed with violence by husbands. This marginal differentiation in attitudes of women towards domestic violence is also observable in urban and rural areas. 54.4% of rural women across the country accepted with domestic abuse, only 46.8% of urban women supported such violence.

Sexual rights are a grave distress for Indian women. Validating this concern, six per cent of women in India and reported to having experienced sexual violence in their lifetime.

Among married women who were victims of sexual violence, 83% claimed that it was because of their present husband and 9% from a former husband as the perpetrators. The form of sexual violence most frequently reported by women was that their partner used corporal force to have sexual intercourse when they did not want to (5.4%). About 4% affirmed that their husband forced them with threats and 3% reported that their husband forced them to perform other sexual acts they did not want to. Husbands and wives being out of the purview of rape laws enable men to 'prey' on

women in the security of her home. These statistics provide a clear indication of the type of sexual harassment and violence young girls and women face in India.

The state of affairs for spinster women is no different. The assessment report highlighted that most common perpetrators of sexual violence on unmarried women were other relatives (27%), followed by a current or former boyfriend (18%), their own friend or acquaintance (17%) and a family friend (11%).

“Sexual violence is most often committed by individuals with whom women have an intimate relationship. Physical violence and sexual violence may not occur in isolation; rather, women may experience a combination of different types of violence,” the survey report said.

Paradoxically, India is one of the 36 countries where marital rape, the act of sexual intercourse with one’s spouse without the spouse’s consent, is still not an immoral offence.

Section 375 of the Indian Penal Code considers mandatory sex in marriage as a crime only when the wife is below age 15. Most of the household violence, sexual violence, and marital rape cases in India are also not at all reported. These cases are disgustingly under-reported by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) data.

The report declared that practice of domestic violence, including physical and sexual violence decreases penetratingly with schooling and education.

By schooling, the percentage of women who report physical violence declined from 38 per cent among women with no schooling to 16 per cent among women with 12 or more years of formal schooling.

Similarly, experience of sexual violence decreases sharply with schooling from eight per cent among women with no schooling to three per cent among women with 12 or more years of schooling. Education will however, not automatically transform in a lower incidence of domestic violence. Cases under “crime against women” increased by 2.9 per cent in 2016 over 2015. Majority of these cases “cruelty by spouse or his relatives” (32.6 per cent) followed by “assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty” (25.0 per cent), “kidnapping and abduction of women” (19.0 per cent) and “rape” (11.5 per cent)

Crime Against Children

Crimes against children have gone up by a whopping 13 per cent, from 94,172 in 2015 to 1,06,958 in 2016. While kidnapping and abduction accounted for 52.3 per cent of the cases, cases under Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, 2012 (POCSO) were at a tormenting 34.4 per cent.

Other Types of Violence and Abuse Against Women

Women experience violence in many ways, from physical abuse to sexual assault and from financial abuse to sexual harassment or trafficking. Whatever form it takes, violence against women can have serious long-term physical and poignant effects.

Violence against women needs to be explicitly explained in a wider social context which permits the the person responsible for to assume the right to use violence as a means of exercising dominance. Therefore, the key mechanism of the dynamics of violence against women is the concepts of gender and power.

Steps to Control Exploitation of Women

1. Build laws and enforce the existing laws to guard women from discrimination
2. Create awareness among public about their responsibilities about national and international human rights laws.

3. Teach women Self employment skills so that they can stand on their own legs without leaning on someone else.
4. Frame peaceful resolution laws to solve the dispute.
5. Give more importance to women's education
6. Give a role to women in decision making
7. Create awareness among public
8. Make punishments severe
9. Educate the future generations on how to respect women
10. Trained counsellors can help domestic abuse victims.

Education Makes a Difference. Irrespective of all the abuse meted to women at their homes, there still could be a solace. Enhance knowledge about younger generations to respect women.

Scope for Future Study

This study can be extended to other foreign countries to have a comparative analysis.

Conclusion

Quite a few of the forms of violence are generally listed by individuals. They are, Given the subordinate status to women, prenatal sex selection, female infanticide, gender violence, physical and sexual abuse, compelled abortion, rapes, honor killings, and mob violence. Incidences like sexual abuse by near relatives, co-habitation with near or dear friends and subsequent decline of marriages and issues relating to illegal pregnancy etc. are the authentic fact, the information of which remains mostly in darkness. In addition, teen students molested by teachers or repeated sexual abuse by antisocial activists are also an ill-fated reality. Women exploitation in the form of physical and mental torture on wives by husband is also common, mostly where women are simply a house wife and not associated with any employment. As a result, they are constrained to stay their head down in a thunderstruck manner tolerating the cruelty of their husband vulnerably.

INDIA HAS BEEN NAMED AS THE MOST DANGEROUS COUNTRY FOR WOMEN IN THE WORLD-IN THE RECENT SURVEY CONDUCTED BY THOMSON REUTERS FOUNDATIONS IN THE YEAR 2018. For rape there is no fixed time in India, women should always be alert. No democracy is a democracy when half of its population lives in fear. Considering the darkness of Democracy, and expressing concern over these figures, National Commission of Women (NCW) chairperson, Rekha Sharma told, "In our society there is lot of restrictions imposed on girls. But now it is enough. Time has come when boys should be taught from childhood how to behave with women as per our social values."

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